

**SIMILARITIES AND DIFFERENCES OF THE CATEGORIES OF NUMBER IN
NOUNS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES**Ilmiy rahbar: **Shavkatov Sherzod Shavkatovich**

Navoiy Davlat Universiteti. PhD

Bahronova Feruza Arslonbek qizi

Navoiy Davlat Universiteti talaba

[@fbahronova7@gmail.com](mailto:fbahronova7@gmail.com)[+998-91-331-11-60](tel:+998913311160)

Annotation: Studying the meaning of number and quantity in nouns is one of the topics which attracts great scientific interest. The main goal of the article is to consider how this linguistic phenomenon is manifested in the Uzbek and English languages and to study the views and conclusions of scientists regarding it. Also, in order to demonstrate a clear comparison of these two languages, relevant examples from Uzbek and English literature are shown.

Key words: noun, singular, plural, number, category

Аннотация: Изучение значения числа и количества в существительных представляет собой большой научный интерес. Основная цель статьи рассмотреть, как данное лингвистическое явление проявляется в узбекском и английском языках, и изучить взгляды и выводы ученых относительно него. Также, чтобы наглядно сравнить уникальный подход этих двух языков, показаны соответствующие примеры из узбекской и английской литературы.

Ключевые слова: существительное, единственное, множественное числительный, категория

Annotatsiya: Ot so'z turkumidagi son-miqdor ma'nosini o'rganish katta ilmiy qiziqishga ega bolgan mavzulardan biri hisoblanadi. Maqolaning asosiy maqsadi esa ushbu lingvistik hodisaning O'zbek va Ingliz tillarida qanday namoyon bo'lishini ko'rib chiqish va unga nisbatan olimlarning qarash va xulosalarini o'rganishdan iborat. Shuningdek, ushbu ikki tilning orziga xos yondashuvini yaqqol solishtirish maqsadida o'zbek va ingliz adabiyotidan tegishli misollar ko'rsatilgan.

Kalitso'zlar: ot, birlik, ko'plik, son, kategoriya

Learnners whose first language is Uzbek sometimes make several mistakes While translating their speech directly into English. The reason for this is the grammatical difference between English and Uzbek languages. Such mistakes are

especially observed regarding the singular and plural meanings of nouns. In this article, we will explore and compare the linguistic peculiarities of both languages.

Number is a grammatical category of nouns which denotes the number of objects, expressed by a word, In English there are two numbers: singular and plural. When it is compared with Uzbek language it should be differentiated like: birlik shakli (singular), ko'plik shakli (plural) [- 287].

"What an excellent **father** you have, girls" [4; 8]

Ina yonib turgan **yulduz** to satdan g'oyib bo ldi. [3; 6]

The singular number is expressed by the absence of a marker. Therefore we say that it is expressed by a zero morpheme [2;19]. As it is possible to see from the examples above in both English and Uzbek languages nouns father and yulduz were used in singular number (birlik shakl) with zero morphemes.

Most nouns in English form their plural by adding suffix **-s** [5;6].

... Their father then went on to the library to write, and the **girls** walked into the breakfast-room [4;374]

Nouns ending in **-s. -ss. -sh, -ch, -x, -o,** take **-es** in the plural [S;6]:

bus-buses

dress-dresses

brush- brushes

torch -torches

box-boxes

I never in my life saw anything more elegant than their **dresses.** [4; 15]

Nouns ending in a vowel + y take -s in the plural. [5;6]

Two girls of six and eight years old, and two younger **boys,** were to be left under the particular care of their cousin Jane. [4; 298]

Nouns ending in a consonant + y, drop the y- and take -ies in the plural: [5;6]:

Such amiable **qualities** must speak for themselves. [4; 12]

Nouns ending in -for-fe, drop the -for -fe and take -ves in the plural. [5;6]:

Here's a short sentence from Emily Dickinson's poem "Nature Rarer Uses

Yellow":

"Wherefore, oh, morning of the yellow leaves?"

In Uzbek language it is formed by suffix -lar [1; 2871,

Bunaqa ruhi pok **odamlar** kam bo'ladi. [3; 7].

But the suffix doesn't always mean plurality.

Sometimes it demonstrates respect or increased exposure:

Shovqindan boshlarim (increased exposure) og`rib ketdi,

Dadamlar (respect) keldilar. [1; 288].

In conclusion, it should be mentioned that grammar of English and Uzbek languages is noticeably different. Nevertheless, in examples above we could find some similarities according to the meaning of number and quantity in nouns.

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